
GEOTECHNICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF SELECTED SOILS FROM EIKA ADAGU NEW LAYOUT AREA IN OKEHI LGA, KOGI STATE, NORTHCENTRAL OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Geotechnical properties of soil has been considered as the first step in prevention of construction failure. The recent infrastructural failure and the influx of people in Eika Adagu area in Okehi LGA of Kogi State area are due to urbanization. In this study we take standard methods to analyze the various soils collected in different parts of Eika Adagu area in Okehi LGA in Kogi State. Representative soil samples were collected from these areas and were investigated for their Geotechnical properties with a view to classifying for their suitability or otherwise for infrastructural development. More so, this has not been done in the selected area. Three representative samples were collected from different locations of the mapped areas around and labeled as soil-A, soil-B and soil-C, all from the area. Characterization based on; moisture content test, Particle size distribution test, Atterberg limit test, Specific gravity test, Compaction test were carried out using the BS 1377, (1990) Parts 1 - 9 specification. Results showed that soil-A and B are clayey soils which are unsuitable for most infrastructural work because they have poor bearing capacities. While soil-C is clayey sand, this could be said to be good for sub-grade material for some construction.

KEYWORDS: *Geotechnical properties, Okehi, atterberg limit, soils*

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INTRODUCTION

The rate at which infrastructures, especially buildings and roads fails today calls for quick attention and lasting solution. The role of Engineering Geologists in providing solution cannot be over emphasized, especially when it comes to foundation construction. The geotechnical properties of soils on which a superstructure is to be constructed must be well understood in order to avoid superstructure and foundation failures (Que et al., 2008; Elueze, 2000; Dazhao, 1986).

Generally, soil is a component of the natural medium that acquires its morphology and properties after a long and slow evolution after reaching an equilibrium with environmental conditions. It is, then, a natural entity, which does not anticipate human use in its evolution. Nevertheless, ever since humans during the Neolithic shifted from hunting and gathering to farming and herding, the soil has undergone intensive exploitation. Some 10,000 years of irrational soil use by humans has transpired, with no objective beyond seeking maximum yield from every kind of soil use. As a result, the soil has reached the present day intensely degraded to the point that a great part of arable land, especially in arid and semiarid regions, is in a situation of irreversible deterioration. To stop this dramatic trend, the only solution is to institute rational soil use—that is, to use each soil in a way that best suits its characteristics and to programme its management for minimal degradation. Much work on the causes of structural failure and soil deformation has been studied (Elueze, 2000; Dazhao, 1985).

Some geologist and scientist in the field soil analysis have attributed their genesis and growth to the influence of human activities on geomorphological processes and qualitative and semi-quantitative methods were employed to produce suggestions for solving the problems (Grove 1951). However investigations carried out by (Egboka and

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Nwankwo, 1985) and Obiefuna *et al.*, (1999) have shown that the primary causes of gully genesis and growth lie in the hydrogeological and geotechnical properties of complex aquifer systems. The high hydrostatic pressure in the aquifers produce a reduction in the effective strength of the unconsolidated coarse sands in the walls of gullies leading to intense erosion (Egboka and Okpoko, 1984; Obiefuna and Nur, 2003).

The main objectives of this research was to carry out the geological and geotechnical assessment of some selected soil from Okehi area in Kogi Central area

Study Area

This study was conducted in Okehi local government area (LGA) of Kogi State, Nigeria. Okehi LGA is located between latitude $7^{\circ} 33'$ and $7^{\circ} 35'$ N and between Longitude $6^{\circ} 10'$ E and $6^{\circ} 14'$ E of the equator (Kogi ADP, 2003). It is located in Kogi Central Senatorial District, between the boundaries of Oyi, Adavi and Okene LGAs of Kogi State. Kogi State is in the southern guinea savanna of the vegetation zones and most centrally located of all Nigerian State (Fejokwu, 1992).

The state has distinct wet and dry seasons. The raining season fall between April and October while the dry season is between November and March (Kogi ADP 2003). Majority of the people in the state are small scale farmers and the rich are diversified soil condition enable agriculture to thrive in the state (Fejokwu 1992).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The material includes: liquid limit (Cassagrande) apparatus, mortar and pistol an electric oven, BS No. 425 sieve, BS (1967), a grooving tool, glass plate, weighing balance, Riffled box, large metal tray, rubber hammer, measuring cylinder, scoop and spatula, water and some numbered specimen containers.

Soil samples collection

The soil sample were collected at four places randomly and were subjected to a number of laboratory tests such as grain size distribution, (Sieve) analysis, petrographic analysis, compaction test and Atterberg or consistency limit test (liquid and plastic limits). The data of annual rain fall was collected from the selected area in the zone.

Geotechnical evaluation

Sieve Analysis:

Representative sample of approximately 500 g was used for the test after washing and oven-dried. The sieving was done by mechanical method using an automatic shakers and a set of sieves.

Atterberg or Consistency Limits

This is defined as the property of the soils which relates to the relative ease to which a soil can be deformed based on the relationship or interaction with water. It is very strong determining factor in measurement of soil utility in the construction area. It give an insight on the nature of the soil as well as the ability of the soil to withstand surface run off water which has a direct bearing in the strength of the soil.

Liquid Limit

This is the water content at which the soil changes from the liquid state to the plastic state. In other words, the liquid limit is defined as a moisture content at which a standard groove cut on a remoulded soil material closes at twenty-five blows of the liquid limit apparatus. The liquid limit was determined using the Casagrande apparatus. In all case, approximately 200 g of the soil samples and were passed through various sieve sizes, after which it was mixed with distilled water to form a uniform paste which was used to carry out this experiment. Some quantity of paste was collected on a spatula into the liquid limit device cup and the face smoothed to a depth of 1.2 cm then a groove was created between the sample and the cup. When the crank of the liquid limit device was turned, the numbers of blows needed to close the groove in the sample for a distance of 1.3cm, the blows were noted. A small sample was then taken from the centre of the closed groove for the moisture content determined. The test was carried out five times to obtain an accurate result at different blows.

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Plastic Limit

This is the water content below which the soil stops behaving as plastic material. In this experiment about 30 g of the sample for Liquid Limit test was used for the plastic limit test at 25 blows. It was then spread for it to lose moisture and mixed thoroughly with distilled water till it become plastic and could be easily molded with the fingers and rolled back and forth between the palm and the glass plate with enough pressure to form a ball. The ball was then rolled into a thread until it reached a diameter of 3mm and crumbled, the moisture content was determined. This test was repeated thrice and the average moisture content calculated as the plastic limit of the soil.

Plasticity Index

The results of the two tests (Liquid limit and Plastic limit) were analyzed and the plasticity index (PT) was obtained as the numerical difference between the liquid limit (LL) and plastic limit (PL) as $PT = LL - PL$.

Compaction test

About 3 kg of the air-dried sample passing through 4.75 mm sieve was taken. Water was added to the soil. Before the commencement of this experiment the mould was cleaned dried and greased lightly and its weight when empty, without the collar, was taken. The wet soil in the tray was divided into three portions. Each portion was put into the mould fitted and to a solid base. The soil was compacted with 25 blows of a 2.6 kg rammer with a free fall of 310 mm evenly distributed over the surface. A second and a third layer was afterward placed for compaction on attaching the collar. The collar was then removed and the soil was trimmed off flush with the top mould. The mass of the mould, base plate and compacted soil was taken and thus the mass of the compacted soil was determined. The bulk and dry densities were later computed from the results this test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Geotechnical properties of the soil in the areas determine their susceptibility to structural or construction failure (Onwuemesi, 1990). The geotechnical parameters of four soil samples from different area that were faced with structural failure were analyzed using Atterberg limits, Sieve and Compaction methods. The difference in liquid limit and plastic limit was used to obtained plasticity index, which is an index to measure plasticity of the soil (Table 1-6).

Soil particle size analysis

Soil consists of an assemblage of discrete particles of different of various shapes and sizes. This is an important tool in the quantification of soil that makes other geotechnical parameter to be valid (Egboka and Nwankwo, 1985). In the evaluation of the particle sizes for the purpose of construction and infrastructural development, a relation between the soil size is key in the field of engineering. Some relevant and useful information can be obtained from a grain size distribution data. Such information includes the percentage larger or finer than a given size and their uniformity or the range in grain size distribution.

Soil has been partition according to unified soil classification system into two main groups: coarse –grained and fine-grained defined by a set of two letters, a prefix and a suffix. The coarse grained designation is assigned to soils for which over 50%, by weight of the material is retained by the no. 200 sieve (0.75mm). Within the coarse grained, the prefix G is assigned to the soils if more than 50%, pass through the no. 4 sieve (4.7mm); G and S is follow by suffix that describes the gradation; W- well graded; P- poorly graded; M- containing silt; C- containing clay. The details of the soil sieve analysis are shown in the table below:

Table A: The particle size of the various soils

	Soil-A	Soil-B	Soil-C
Sieve No(mm)	Wt(g)	Wt(g)	Wt(g)
4.0	0.0	0.4	0.0
2.0	0.0	0.1	4.2
1.0	0.0	0.3	15.5
500	5.2	0.6	9.7
250	32.0	2.8	5.6
125	11.8	13.6	3.9
63	0.5	22.8	3.4
Silt	0.3	9.8	7.4
Total			

Soil samples are designated as: soil A, soil B and soil C

Specific gravity

The various soil samples and their specific gravity are shown in (Table 7), the values range from 1.98 - 2.56. Specific gravity is an important index property of soils that is closely linked with mineralogy and/or chemical composition. Research has shown that specific gravity of soils and their degree of laterization. On the basis of the classification by (Onwuemesi, 1990; Daniel and Wu, 1993) the soils fall within either sand, silt or clay type of soil with some containing mica or iron. The soils are also not organic.

Atterberg Limit:

The Atterberg limits are an empirically developed but widely used procedure for establishing and describing the consistency of cohesive soil thereby providing useful information regarding soil strength, behaviour, stability and type and state of consolidation besides its use to identify the soil classification (Ola, 1983; Oladeji and Raheem, 2002). Consistency is frequently used to describe the degree of firmness (e.g soft, medium, firm, or hard) and the consistency of cohesive soil is strongly affected by the water content of the soil. A gradual increase of the water content, for example, may transform dry clay from perhaps a solid state to a semi-solid state, to a plastic state and after further moisture increase, increase into a liquid state (Stephen et al., 2012; Egboka and Nwankwo, 1985).

The results of the Atterberg limit are shown in Table 1-6. The consistency limits have been repeatedly shown to be useful indicators of clay behavior (Onwuemesi, 1990; Stephen et al., 2012). Certain types of clayey soils expand when they are wetted and shrink when dried. According to the classification by federal ministry of work and housing, only one out of the four soil passed the results, while other were said to below the acceptable standard for the construction houses as well in road construction (Bello et al., 2007).

The plasticity index of the soil which is the difference in water content between the liquid and plastic limits is a measure of the affinity of a soil for water. It is an indicator of the plasticity of a soil. These depend greatly on the data obtained from the liquid limit. The greater the plasticity index, the more plastic and compressible and the greater the volume change characteristics of the soil.

Compaction characteristics: The compaction characteristics of soils are determined to ensure quality of materials used for construction purposes. The soils for the present study were compacted at the modified AASH-TO level of compaction. The maximum dry densities of the soils are shown in Table 7.

CONCLUSION

Geotechnical investigations of the different soil from Eika Adagu in Okehi LGA were study for the purpose of inferring the surface and subsurface processes that contribute to the infrastructural failure in the area. Base on the result obtained, it is clearly evidence that the soil is largely well sorted with low content of fine grain material such as silt and clays that provide cohesion. These hence made the soil loose and susceptible to structural failure. We

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suggest that additional material that can improve the soil properties need to be added to ensure effective utilization of the soil for construction purposes.

Table 1: Liquid Limit properties for Soil- A

CONTAINER	MASS OF CONTAINER (g)	NO OF BLOW	MASS OF CONTAINER +WET SAMPLE (g)	MASS OF CONTAINER +DRY SAMPLE (g)	MASS OF WET SAMPLE (g)	MASS OF DRY SAMPLE (g)	MASS OF WATER (g)	MASS OF CONTENT (%)	LIQUID LIMIT (%)
G	49	30	73.8	63.8	24.8	14.8	10.0	67.56	
D	42.6	30	69.4	59.4	26.8	16.8	10.0	59.52	
L	51.9	27	82.3	70.6	30.4	18.7	11.7	62.56	70.2
F	43.4	25	64.8	54.9	21.4	11.5	9.9	86.1	
C	37.5	23	60.4	50.2	22.9	12.7	10.2	80.3	

G, D, L, F and C were representative of the container for the soil

Table 2: Plastic limit properties for Soil- A

CONTAINER	MASS OF CONTAINER (g)	MASS OF CONTAINER + WET SAMPLE(g)	MASS OF CONTAINER + DRY SAMPLE(g)	MASS OF WET SAMPLE(g)	MASS OF DRY SAMPLE(g)	MASS OF WATER(g)	MASS OF CONTENT (%)	PLASTIC LIMIT (%) (PL)
T	13.6	16.4	15.7	2.7	2.1	0.7	33	
H	13.7	16.3	15.7	2.6	2.0	0.6	30	28.3
Z	13.2	15.4	13.6	1.8	0.4	0.4	20	

T, H, and Z were representative of the container for the soil

Plasticity Index (PI) = Liquid Limit (LL) – Plastic Limit (PL)

PI=LL-PL = 70.2-28.3 =PI=41.9

Table 3: Liquid Limit properties for Soil- B

CONTAINER	MASS OF CONTAINER (g)	NO OF BLOW	MASS OF CONTAINER +WET SAMPLE (g)	MASS OF CONTAINER +DRY SAMPLE (g)	MASS OF WET SAMPLE (g)	MASS OF DRY SAMPLE (g)	MASS OF WATER (g)	MASS OF CONTENT (%)	LIQUID LIMIT (%)
A	32	20	59.5	49.6	27.5	17.6	9.9	56.25	
OQ	53.0	22	78.3	69.1	25.3	15.1	10.2	66.2	
TR	42.2	20	67.6	56.4	25.4	14.2	11.2	78.87	59.8
L	32.4	18	57.5	48.0	25.1	15.6	9.99.5	60.89	
D	52.4	17	77.3	67.3	24.9	14.9	10.0	67.1	

A, OQ, TR, L and D were representative of the container for the soil

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Table 4: Plastic limit properties for Soil- B

CONTAINER	MASS OF CONTAINER (g)	MASS OF CONTAINER + WET SAMPLE(g)	MASS OF CONTAINER + DRY SAMPLE(g)	MASS OF WET SAMPLE(g)	MASS OF DRY SAMPLE(g)	MASS OF WATER(g)	MASS OF CONTENT (%)	PLASTIC LIMIT (%) (PL)
WZ	13.5	15.1	14.6	1.6	1.1	0.5	45.45	
N	13.1	14.7	14.1	1.6	1.0	0.6	33.3	38.35%
Z	13.6	15.1	14.3	1.5	1.1	0.4	36.3	

WZ, N and Z were representative of the container for the soil

$$PI=LL-PL = 59.8-38.35 = PI=21.45$$

Where PI = plasticity index, LL= liquid limit and PL= plastic limit

Table 5: Liquid Limit properties for Soil- C

CONTAINER	MASS OF CONTAINER (g)	NO OF BLOW	MASS OF CONTAINER + WET SAMPLE (g)	MASS OF CONTAINER + DRY SAMPLE (g)	MASS OF WET SAMPLE (g)	MASS OF DRY SAMPLE (g)	MASS OF WATER (g)	MASS OF CONTENT (%)	LIQUID LIMIT (%)
N	49	33	64.8	57.1	15.8	8.1	7.7	95.06	
Z	42.6	27	73.8	58.3	30.8	15.7	14.7	93.63	
K	51.6	30	69.7	61.0	17.8	9.1	8.7	95.60	95%
O	43.4	27	58.5	51.0	15.1	7.6	7.5	98.68	
W	37.5	30	54.4	46.1	16.9	8.6	8.5	96.51	

N, Z, K, O and W were representative of the container for the soil

Table 6: Plastic limit properties for Soil- C

CONTAINER	MASS OF CONTAINER (g)	MASS OF CONTAINER + WET SAMPLE(g)	MASS OF CONTAINER + DRY SAMPLE(g)	MASS OF WET SAMPLE(g)	MASS OF DRY SAMPLE(g)	MASS OF WATER(g)	MASS OF CONTENT (%)	PLASTIC LIMIT (%) (PL)
T	13.6	14.4	14.1	0.8	0.2	0.6	40	
Y	13.7	14.4	14.2	0.7	0.5	0.2	40	60%
R	13.2	14.0	13.6	0.8	0.4	0.4	100	

T, Y and R were representative of the container for the soil

$$PI=LL-PL = PL= 95-60 = PL=35\%$$

Table 7: Compaction and Specific gravity test

	OMC %	MDD (kg/m ³)	Specific gravity
Soil-A	9.8	2.31	2.56
Soil-B	11.5	2.81	2.43
Soil-C	12.9	2.11	1.98

OMC= optimum moisture content % , MDD= maximum dry density

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